

Light induced lactose/maltose – methylene blue reaction in flow reactors

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Abstract : Reactions between disaccharide (lactose, maltose) and a photosensitive methylene blue (MB) in an alkaline medium have been studied in a Continuously Stirred Tank Reactor (CSTR) and result was compared with that of batch reactor experiments. During the reaction, color change in the sequence, blue \rightleftharpoons colorless was observed. The blue form of the solution corresponds to the high potential state while the colorless (reduced form) corresponds to the low potential state. Experiment was performed in the complete darkness as well as in presence of light of 17 Lux intensity. It was observed that the rate of redox reaction increased in the presence of light due to absorption of photon. The frequency of oscillation in the light was more than that in the complete darkness. Influence of dense matrix such as polyethylene glycol on redox potential changes with time has been investigated. Potential changes with time were also monitored in CSTR at different flow rates. The residence time k_0 was varied in the range 0.0062–0.0500 min⁻¹.

Keywords : Light induced reactions, methylene blue reactions, lactose, maltose.

Far from equilibrium phenomena, including temporal and spatio-temporal oscillations are of considerable current interest in chemical dynamics¹. Such oscillating phenomena are very interesting from the view point of non-linear sciences. Pattern formation processes are of interest from the view point of many disciplines ranging from chemistry, physics, medicines and biology². Earliest pattern formation phenomena are the ring of periodic precipitation, studied by various workers³. Recently, attention has been given by the stationary symmetry breaking patterns first described by Turing in 1952. Spatio-temporal pattern formation in molecular evolution leads to new phenomena⁴. The oxidation reaction of sugars by methylene blue using some carbohydrates under alkaline conditions was investigated by several other workers⁵.

In the present paper we report the light induced oxidation reaction of lactose and maltose by highly photosensitive methylene blue in an alkaline conditions in a CSTR at different experimental conditions. Influence of a dense matrix has also been studied at different flow rates.

Experimental

Materials : Lactose (SDS Laboratory, A.R.), sodium hydroxide (s.d. fine Chem. Ltd., India, L.R.), maltose (s.d. fine Chem. Ltd., India, L.R.), methylene blue (Qualigens), polyethylene glycol (s.d. fine Chem. Ltd., India, m.w. 4000), x-t recorder (Digital Electronics, India), platinum and calomel electrodes (Toshniwal, India) were used.

Procedure for the study of temporal oscillations in CSTR : Carbohydrate (lactose, maltose, 0.5 M), sodium hydroxide (0.08 M) and methylene blue (2.2×10^{-4} M) were fed to the Continuously Stirred Tank Reactor (CSTR) at definite flow rates from the reservoirs R₁ and R₂ through polythene tubing as shown in Fig. 1(b). The level of the solution in the CSTR was kept constant by a continuous outflow of solutions through an outlet 'O'. The solution in the CSTR was stirred at a speed ~400 rpm. Visual oscillations in color (blue \rightleftharpoons colorless) were immediately observed. Since the temperature change in the oscillatory system was found to be insignificant (<1 °C), experiments with CSTR were performed at room tem-

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. Experimental setup of (a) Batch reactor and (b) Continuously Stirred Tank Reactor to monitor potential changes with time: (C) Calomel electrode, (P) Platinum electrode, (R₁ and R₂) the reservoirs and (C₁, C₂) are control knobs, (R) x-t recorder and (M) magnetic stirrer.

perature. The reaction was followed by noting the potential change of the Pt electrode with reference to the calomel electrode by using x-t recorder. Experiment was also performed in a batch reactor using an experimental setup shown in Fig. 1(a). 10 ml of thoroughly mixed solution containing disaccharide (lactose or maltose, 0.08 M), sodium hydroxide (0.5 M), methylene blue (2.2×10^{-4} M) were taken in a Corning petridish, which was open to atmosphere to allow the passage of oxygen. The thickness of the solution was ~ 0.19 mm. Experiment was performed in the presence of natural light. Intensity of light was measured with the help of a Luxmeter (LM1010,

Germany). Calomel and platinum electrodes (diameter 0.5 mm) were put into a petridish containing the above solution and connected with x-t recorder.

Fig. 2 show potential changes with time in batch and flow reactors for lactose. To study the influence of light on the reaction, experiment was also performed in the complete darkness as well as in the presence of light of 17 Lux intensity in a batch reactor.

The oscillatory characteristics also depend on the magnitude of the residence time k_0 (k_0 is defined as the ratio of flow rate and total volume of the reactor). Experiments with lactose were performed in the k_0 range $0.0062-0.050 \text{ min}^{-1}$. Results are shown in Fig. 3. Similar experiments were also performed in presence of PEG, which was influxed in the reactor with MB and water.

Results and discussion

When a carbohydrate such as lactose or maltose was added to an aqueous solution of NaOH along with a small amount of methylene blue and shaken thoroughly, it turned blue. After standing for a short time, the solution fades to colorless indicating that the dye has been reduced by the carbohydrate. Lactose and maltose in an alkaline medium give protons and electrons as given in Schemes 1 and 2.

These protons and electrons subsequently reduce the methylene blue to the leuco form according to the scheme

During this process, the potential also oscillates with time and color changes in the sequence blue \rightleftharpoons colorless. Blue form of the solution is due to reduced form of methylene blue (high potential state) while the colorless form is due to its oxidized form which is in the low potential state. Experiment was performed in the presence of natural light of 17 Lux intensity.

An identical experiment was also performed in the complete darkness. On comparison of results, indicates that (i) nature oscillations in the two cases is quite differ-

Fig. 2. Redox potential changes as a function of time in (a) Batch reactor and (b) CSTR. Flow rate = 2 ml/min, residence time ($k_0 = \text{flow rate}/\text{volume of the reactor}$) = 0.025 min^{-1} . Conditions : [lactose] = 0.08 M , [NaOH] = 0.5 M , [MB] = $2.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$. Intensity of light = 17 Lux.

Fig. 3. Dependence of flow rate on redox potential changes as a function of time in a CSTR : (a) $k_o = 0.0062 \text{ min}^{-1}$, flow rates $Q_{\text{Lactose}} = 0.5 \text{ ml/min}$, $Q_{\text{NaOH}} = 0.5 \text{ ml/min}$, $Q_{\text{MB}} = 0.5 \text{ ml/min}$; (b) $k_o = 0.025 \text{ min}^{-1}$, flow rates $Q_{\text{Lactose}} = 2 \text{ ml/min}$, $Q_{\text{NaOH}} = 2 \text{ ml/min}$, $Q_{\text{MB}} = 2 \text{ ml/min}$; (c) $k_o = 0.050 \text{ min}^{-1}$, flow rates $Q_{\text{Lactose}} = 4 \text{ ml/min}$, $Q_{\text{NaOH}} = 4 \text{ ml/min}$, $Q_{\text{MB}} = 4 \text{ ml/min}$. The volume of the reactor was 80 ml, sensitivity 10 mv/inch, chart speed 2.5 min/inch. Conditions : [lactose] = 0.08 M, [NaOH] = 0.5 M, [MB] = $2.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$. Intensity of light = 17 Lux.

ent and (ii) the frequency of oscillations in the light is more than that in the complete darkness. It indicates that the rate of redox reaction is enhanced in the presence of light due to absorption of photon according to the following scheme :

Experiment described above was carried out in a petridish with solution depth ~ 1.9 mm. We may call it as a batch reactor (Fig. 1a). In this case, the concentration of reactants may decrease continuously during the reaction and stop after some time. Thus, in order to maintain the solution concentration constant through out the experiment and to maintain the system far from thermodynamic equilibrium for a longer duration. A continuously stirred tank reactor as shown in Fig. 1b and described in the experimental section, has been employed. In the CSTR, the carbohydrate, NaOH, and MB were continuously fed from the reservoirs to the reactor at a fixed flow rate at room temperature. Potential changes with time for the carbohydrates lactose and maltose were monitored. Fig. 2 is a representation of curves for lactose. In a batch reactor experiment, although, the oscillation in potential was observed but at the same time potential decreased as shown in Figs. 2(a) due to the formation of $\text{MB}_{\text{Leuco form}}$ resulting in the shift in redox equilibrium. In case of CSTR, oscillations in potential were monitored as a function of time. A drastic change in potential-time plots were observed. Instead of decrease in potential, an increase in potential was observed in case of CSTR. Result is shown in Fig. 2(b). Temporal oscillations at different flow rates were also studied. The residence time k_0 was varied in the range $0.0062\text{--}0.0500$ min^{-1} (Fig. 3). Experiment was also performed in presence of a gel matrix such as PEG (8×10^{-4} M) due to the following advantages : (i) hydrodynamic convection is eliminated in gel systems, (ii) within a gel matrix, a variety of chemical species can be immobilized and (iii) gel materials offer bubble free systems for a longer duration.

Results show that in the presence of PEG, the rate of reaction is reduced. The blue color of the solution disappears in ~ 120 s while in the absence of PEG this time was only 60 s. The pattern first appears in ~ 145 s while in the absence of PEG this time was only ~ 90 s. Redox potential of the system was considerably reduced in the presence of PEG. Similar experiments were also performed with another disaccharides maltose. A little difference in the experimental results may be due to the structural and morphological differences of the two disaccharides. Although, there is great similarity between lactose and maltose but in case of lactose (4-O- β -D-galactopyranosyl-D-glucopyranose), a molecule of D(+) glucose and a molecule of D(+) galactose are linked together by 4-O- β -D linkage while in case of maltose (4-O- α -D-glucopyranosyl-D-glucopyranose) having two glucose units are linked together by 4-O- β -D linkage.

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